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**Towards climate-smart sustainable management of
agricultural soils**

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DELIVERABLE LEADER: CREA (Italy): Simone Bregaglio (simoneugomaria.bregaglio@crea.gov.it)

CONTRIBUTING PARTNERS TO THIS REPORT: CREA (Italy): Roberta Calone (roberta.calone@crea.gov.it)

CREA (Italy): Luisa Maria Manici (luisamaria.manici@crea.gov.it)

LUKE (Finland) Elena Valkama (elena.valkama@luke.fi)

UNIMI (Italy) Marco Acutis (marco.acutis@unimi.it)

UNIMI (Italy) Alessia Perego (alessia.perego@unimi.it)

UNIMI (Italy) Marco Botta (marco.botta@unimi.it)

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List of Abbreviation

Abbreviation	Description
C	Carbon
N	Nitrogen
ΔC	Change in soil carbon stock
SOC	Soil Organic Carbon
GHG	Greenhouse gases
N ₂ O	Nitrous oxide
NO ₃	Nitrate
OF	Organic farming
CF	Conventional farming

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1. Background

Balancing agricultural productivity with environmental sustainability - particularly concerning soil organic carbon (SOC) loss, greenhouse gas emissions, and groundwater contamination - remains a significant challenge for European agriculture. In response, the European Commission launched the Farm to Fork strategy within the broader European Green Deal, aiming to foster sustainable growth through inclusive and resilient food systems. Central to this strategy is organic farming (OF) (Billen et al., 2024). Although conceptualized in the early 20th century as a countermeasure to the limitations of conventional farming (CF), OF still lacks universally standardized practices. According to the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO), OF is a holistic production system that enhances agroecosystem health by promoting biodiversity, biological cycles, and soil biological activity, largely replacing synthetic chemicals with natural inputs and mechanical methods (FAO/WHO Codex Alimentarius Commission, 1999).

The Farm to Fork strategy sets an ambitious target: by 2030, at least 25% of EU agricultural land should be managed organically. Between 2012 and 2022, the share of organic farmland in the EU increased by over 79% reaching 16.9 million hectares of agricultural land in 2022, with France, Spain, Italy, and Germany leading and collectively accounting for 56% of the total. The Nordic countries have developed strong organic farming sectors and are recognized as leaders in ecological practices. Sweden leads with 20.2% of its agricultural land certified organic, followed by Finland (14.4%), Denmark (11.4%), and Norway (4.6%) (Paull & Tuttunen, 2024). Notably, Sweden had the highest shares of organic cereals and fresh vegetable production in 2022 (Eurostat). However, these regions are also experiencing drastic land-use changes, particularly the conversion of forests to cropland, leading to net SOC depletion as decomposition surpasses the accumulation of agriculture-derived carbon (C) in the soil (Akujärvi et al., 2014; Neset et al., 2019). OF is expected to play an increasingly crucial role in mitigating these effects and supporting sustainable agriculture in the new converted area, especially given the projected growing importance of Nordic agriculture in future food production under changing climate conditions (Fogelfors et al., 2009; Wiréhn, 2018).

Despite progress, the growth rate of organic agriculture remains insufficient to meet the 2030 target. However, studies by Morais et al. (2021) and Muller et al. (2017) suggest that global food security could be achieved through organic agriculture by 2050, provided that specific combinations of agroecological strategies are implemented. A key challenge to address is the ability of organic farms to balance environmental sustainability with economic viability. On average, organic yields are 5% to 30% lower than conventional yields and generally require more labor to attain comparable outputs (De Ponti et al., 2012; Ponisio et al., 2015). Furthermore, organic farming is knowledge-intensive (Bliss et al., 2019), requiring site-specific adaptations to diverse pedoclimatic conditions and production systems (Seufert & Ramankutty, 2017), which presents an additional barrier to scaling up its adoption.

On the other hand, organic farming has been shown to achieve significantly higher yields than conventional farming under abiotic stress conditions, such as drought and salinity (Borron, 2006; Gopinath et al., 2018; Kundel et al., 2020; Lotter et al., 2003). The soil microbiome plays a crucial role in determining sustainable agricultural productivity and plant resilience (Barrios, 2007; Van Der Heijden et al., 2008). A meta-analysis by Lori et al., (2017) demonstrated that organic farming promotes greater microbial abundance and enhanced microbial activities (e.g., dehydrogenase, protease, and urease) compared to conventional farming. However, the effects of agricultural management on the soil microbiome are complex and varied (Bünemann et al., 2006; Nelson & Spaner, 2010), making it challenging to derive universally valid conclusions regarding organic and conventional farming systems.

While experimental trials have provided valuable insights into organic farming practices effect on soil and plant productivity, they are often limited in scope and duration and can be resource-intensive. Process-based models offer a powerful and relatively new alternative, simulating the impacts of management practices across various spatial and temporal scales. Since their inception in the early 1960s, these models have been used to simulate crop-associated processes in response to environmental factors (Asseng et al., 2014), as well as agroforestry systems, greenhouse gas emissions, soil nitrogen (N), C, and water dynamics, and other physicochemical properties (Wimalasiri et al., 2023), thereby supporting decision-making. With the increasing

availability of fine-scale global data on current and future climatic conditions, these models also facilitate the assessment of climate change impacts and the evaluation of alternative management strategies before their implementation (Bassu et al., 2014; Lobell & Asseng, 2017)

This report has two primary objectives:

- To utilize the process-based ARMOSA crop model to evaluate the effects of two production systems (crop-production farms vs. livestock-production farms) and two agricultural management practices (conventional vs. organic) on soil C sequestration, nitrous oxide (N₂O) emissions, nitrate (NO₃) leaching, and crop yields under both current and future climatic conditions (2040 - 2069 and 2070 - 2100) in northern Europe. The results aim to contribute to a deeper understanding of the long-term benefits and limitations of organic farming from multiple perspectives, particularly in relation to soil processes in the context of a changing climate.
- To leverage results from a controlled phytotron experiment to assess soil microbial population dynamics in response to extreme soil temperature and moisture conditions under two climate change scenarios based on IPCC projections. The experimental data obtained will inform the development of response function curves necessary for integrating microbial dynamics into the ARMOSA model, thereby enhancing its ability to accurately simulate the impact of microbial processes on soil health, nutrient cycling, and carbon sequestration. While this integration is a complex and ongoing task, the findings presented in this report will provide a preliminary overview of expected microbial responses to extreme environmental conditions, establishing a crucial foundation for future model enhancements.

- **Materials and Methods**

1.1. ARMOSA application to simulate different AE practices in current and future climatic

1.1.1. Case Study

The case study was located in the South Savo region of Finland, in Mikkeli. The local climate is classified as subarctic (Dfc) according to the Köppen-Geiger system, and as boreal according to Metzger et al. (2005). The area experiences an average annual temperature of 4.7°C and an annual precipitation of 707 mm, with the highest monthly rainfall in July (87 mm). The soil

selected for this simulation was loamy sand, consisting of 76% sand, 4% clay, and 20% silt, based on the Finnish classification system (Yli-Halla et al., 2000). This soil texture corresponds to sandy Aquic Haplocryod in Soil Taxonomy (Yli-Halla and Mokma, 2015), with a soil C content of 3.5%, a C/N ratio of 17, and a pH of 6.2 in the top 30 cm. Below 30 cm, the soil maintained a similar texture but had a reduced C content (0.8%).

A five-year crop rotation was designed to reflect common agricultural practices in both conventional (C) and organic (O) systems in the region, representative of crop and livestock production farms. For crop production farms, the rotation included cereals such as spring barley (*Hordeum vulgare*), oats (*Avena sativa*), rye (*Secale cereale*), and spring wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), along with oilseed rape and meadow hay, with fodder pea included in organic rotations. Livestock farm rotations, instead, consisted of two years of cereals followed by three years of meadow hay, with fescue and timothy as the primary species, and clover incorporated in organic systems. Nine different scenarios (Table 1) were simulated, involving varying combinations of residue management strategies (retained or removed) and fertilization practices.

In conventional systems, mineral fertilizers were applied alone or combined with slurry, while organic systems used combinations of slurry, green manure, and a meat and bone meal-based commercial organic fertilizer (Ecolan Agra®). Fertilizer application rates were determined based on regional N fertilizer sales data from 1999 to 2018 (Luke Statistics database).

For crop farms, three conventional systems (CC+R, CC-R, CC2+R) and two organic systems (CO+R, CO2+R) were modelled. Conventional systems varied by residue management and fertilizer type, with either mineral fertilizer alone or a combination of slurry and mineral fertilizer, as described in Table 1. For organic systems, Ecolan and green manure (in PO2+R) were applied.

In livestock farms, two conventional (LC+R, LC-R) and two organic systems (AO+R, AO-R) were simulated with similar variations in residue management and fertilization practices (Table 1).

Table 1. Scheme of simulated 5-year crop rotations in the crop production (C) and livestock production (L) farms under conventional (C) and organic (O) management, with details on residue management and the amount of inorganic and organic fertilization applied.

Farm type	Rotation	Residue management	N fertilization (kg ha ⁻¹)	Year 1	Year 2	Year 3	Year 4	Year 5
CROP PRODUCTION (C)	CONVENTIONAL							
	CC+R	Incorporated	crop: 80 mineral hay: 120 mineral	barley	oilseed rape	oat	meadow hay	wheat
	CC-R	Removed				meadow hay		
	CC2+R	Incorporated	crop: 40 slurry + 40 mineral hay: 80 slurry + 40 mineral					
	ORGANIC							
	CO+R	Incorporated	oilseed rape: 40 Ecolan	barley	oat	ryegrass + clover as green manure	rye	ryegrass
CO2+R	Incorporated	oilseed rape: 40 Ecolan rye: 40 Ecolan barley/pea: 30 Ecolan oat/pea: 30 Ecolan	pea	pea	oilseed rape			
LIVESTOCK PRODUCTION (L)	CONVENTIONAL							
	LC+R	Incorporated	crop: 40 mineral + 40 slurry hay: 80 mineral + 75 slurry	oat	timothy-fescue hay			barley
	LC-R	Removed						
	ORGANIC							
	LO+R	Incorporated	crop: 80 slurry hay: 155 slurry	oat	timothy-fescue hay + clover as green manure			barley
LO-R	Removed							

1.1.2. ARMOSA Model Calibration and Validation

Simulations were conducted using the ARMOSA process-based crop model (Perego et al., 2013), which has been already successfully used in Finland (Valkama et al., 2020). ARMOSA simulates crop development and growth at a daily time step with an approach based on light interception and net photosynthesis, soil water dynamics using the Richards' equation, and changes in time of bulk density and hydrological characteristics according to the tillage operation and the changes in the soil organic matter. Carbon and N cycle (including mineralization, immobilization,

nitrification, denitrification, and leaching) are simulated with an approach that preserves the difference between the different typologies of crop residues incorporated in the soil and organic fertilizers (Pirttioja et al., 2015).

The model was calibrated and validated using long-term yield data from 20–21 years for conventionally managed barley, oats, wheat, rye, and grass, and 5–6 years for organic barley, oats, and oilseed rape yields (Luke Statistics database, 2021). The calibration was informed by previous studies conducted in Jokioinen (270 km southwest of Mikkeli; Valkama et al., 2020). Key parameters calibrated included the maximum CO₂ assimilation rate under light saturation, the N dilution curve, which determines minimal, critical, and maximum N concentrations, and the water stress sensitivity coefficient.

1.1.3. Simulation Scenarios

Three simulation scenarios (Figure 1) were set up, one for the current climatic conditions (1999 - 2022), and two for future climate projections (2040 - 2069 and 2070 - 2100). Daily data on maximum and minimum temperatures, precipitation, and global solar radiation for the period 1999 - 2022 were collected from a meteorological station in Mikkeli (61°41'N, 027°16'E, 85 m asl). For future scenarios, 30 synthetic years of weather variables climate projections were based on the RCP 4.5 pathway and obtained from the HadGEM2 global climate model, accessed via the BONARES repository. For Mikkeli, these climate scenarios project an increase in annual rainfall by 40 mm and 70 mm, respectively, along with a rise in mean annual temperature by 2.9°C and 3.3°C.

Figure 1. Monthly mean cumulated precipitation and mean temperature for the current climate conditions and future climate scenarios in Mikkeli, South Savo region of Finland.

1.1.4. Trade-Off Analysis

The simulation outputs were used to evaluate and compare nine different crop rotations based on total crop yield over the five-year rotation ($\text{kg ha}^{-1} 5\text{yr}^{-1}$), changes in soil C stock (ΔC , $\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$), annual N_2O emissions ($\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$), and NO_3 leaching to groundwater ($\text{kg ha}^{-1} \text{yr}^{-1}$). For yield comparison, biomass values (kg ha^{-1}) were converted to gross sellable yields (€ ha^{-1}) to account

for differences in the economic value of various crops. This adjustment was necessary to avoid bias, as perennial meadow crops produce high biomass with lower economic value, while annual cereals generate less biomass but higher economic returns. Selling prices for 2022 and 2023 were sourced from EUROSTAT for Finland. In cases where data were unavailable, such as for meadow hay, prices were estimated indirectly from German data by using the ratio of barley prices between Finland and Germany.

To differentiate between conventional and organic systems, a 36% price premium was applied to organic crop prices. This increment was estimated by comparing barley price data under conventional and organic farming management, as reported in the LUKE Statistics database for 2021 - 2023.

The trade-off analysis was conducted using the fuzzy logic-based Σ ommit index (Calone et al., 2024), which integrates the four analysed factors into a composite metric ranging from 0 (least sustainable) to 1 (most sustainable). The analysis was applied under current climate conditions, as well as for future climate scenarios. In addition, for simulation under current climatic conditions, three further versions of the Σ ommit index were applied to represent different stakeholder perspectives, each with distinct weightings for the four trade-off components. These weighting schemes are described in the main reference paper (Calone et al., 2024).

All data analyses were performed using the R Studio environment.

1.2. Simulations of soil microbiome response to extreme events

Two different climatic change scenarios established according to IPCC simulations, taking as reference the climatic conditions of the eastern Po Valley in northern Italy as described in (Manici et al., 2016), were simulated using a ploughed soil under conventional crop rotation in central Po valley (Italy). A 60-growing period simulating cold spring and warm spring was set by changing every 15 days the temperature regimes. The latest was a loam-silty soil classified as Udifluventic Haplustepts fine silty, mixed mesic (U.S. Department of Agriculture, 2006).

After a preliminary experiment in which two extreme conditions (flooding and drought) were tested in the phytotron on wheat and maize (M41-M43 of the EJPSOIL) and the methodology to

monitoring soil water content using suitable probes and remote data recording was set up, two final simulation cycles were planned. Wheat was adopted as target crop due to its better performance in the preliminary in phytotron simulation under extreme conditions.

Warm and cold spring temperature regimes were tested in phytotron with two subsequent cycles at three water content levels as described in Table 2 and shown in Figure 2.

Table 2. Basic scheme of the soil treatments adopted for simulations in phytotron

Treatment	Water content	Temperature
Prolonged drought	(20% Field capacity - FC)	Extreme event 1
Prolonged wet conditions	(110% Field capacity - FC)	Extreme event 2
Optimal growth conditions.	(80% Field capacity - FC)	Control

A 60-days growing period to simulate cold spring, and warm spring was set by changing every 15 days the temperature regimes as reported in Table 3.

Table 3. Temperature sequences adopted to obtain in phytotron cold and warm spring.

Day/night (h)	Cold spring		Warm spring	
	Day (°C)	Night (°C)	Day (°C)	Night (°C)
12/12	13	8	18	12
13/11	15	10	20	14
14/10	17	12	22	16
15/9	19	14	24	18

The first experiment was carried out by growing wheat for 60 days at the water content of the basic scheme (Tables 2 and 3), applying cold spring (M45-M46 of the ARTEMIS project) conditions (Table 3). The second, warm spring, started at the M52 of the ARTEMIS project.

Figure 2. View of the growing cycle in the phytotron at three soil water content monitored with the support of probes and continuous remote acquisition of water content data.

The experimental setting of each cycle consisted of a total of 30 pots for a 60-day growing period, after a pre-period of 15 days during which pots, after wheat sown, were maintained at the same temperature and soil water content (22 °C and 80% field capacity) in order to guarantee that seedlings reached the two-leaf stage.

Based on results of the preliminary trial, soil sampling was performed only at the end of the 60-day trial period because it was the minimum period required for a stable variation of microbial communities in these in-pot simulations. Soil sampling was carried out in the rhizo-head area of wheat (Figure 3).

Figure 3. Soil sampling at the end of the in-pot trial in phytotron in the three soil water content treatments.

After soil DNA extraction, the quantitative response of total fungi and bacteria were quantified using digital PCR as described in (Manici et al., 2024) and real-time PCR respectively as described in (Manici et al., 2022) and expressed in term of number of DNA copies per μl of soil DNA.

This DNA-based quantification of fungal and bacteria in soil allowed a more accurate evaluation of soil functioning variation in response to simulated climatic change as compared to conventional approaches to date used such chloroform fumigation-extraction (CFE) and substrate-induced respiration (SIR) (Semenov et al., 2018).

2. Results and discussions

2.1. Analysis of ARMOSA output for the selected trade-off components

The stacked bar plot in Figure 4 illustrates the average gross saleable product ($\text{€ ha}^{-1} 5\text{y}^{-1}$) for each rotation system, disaggregated by crop type. Under current conditions (1999–2022), organically managed systems (O) achieved the highest gross saleable product ($> \text{€}4,000 \text{ ha}^{-1}$), both in crop (CO+R, CO2+R) and livestock (LO+R, LO-R) production rotations. The application of commercial organic fertilizer to all crops in the CO2+R rotation resulted in a modest yield increase (+4.6%) compared to CO+R, where the fertilizer was applied exclusively to oilseed rape. The inclusion of leguminous crops mixed with cereals (e.g., barley + pea and oat + pea) significantly boosted total gross saleable yields of oat (+49%) and barley (+30%) compared to the same rotations where these crops were cultivated alone. Conversely, the integration of mineral fertilizers with slurry in CC2+R led to lower yields ($< \text{€}3,500 \text{ ha}^{-1}$) compared to the same rotation with only mineral fertilizer application (CC+R and CC-R). Crop residue removal did not appear to significantly affect the final saleable output.

In future climate scenarios, a decline in gross saleable product was observed across most systems, with crop production under organic management (CO2+R and CO+R) showing the largest decreases (-46% and -45% respectively in 2070-2100 scenario), followed by conventional management systems (CC2+R -31%, CC-R -26%, and CC+R -26% in 2070-2100 scenario). The reduction was most pronounced for annual crops such as barley, wheat, and rye, and to a lesser extent oats. Significant reductions were also observed in mixed cereal-leguminous crops. Conversely, meadow hay showed a slight increase in yield over time. In livestock farms, cereal yields declined under future scenarios, but the three-year meadow hay yields increased, to the extent that, by 2070 - 2100, total gross saleable yield surpasses current levels. Systems with meadow hay, which remains on the soil for three years, exhibited greater resilience, particularly in organic systems. The increase in meadow yields may result from its extended soil cover period, allowing earlier growth and prolonged biomass production compared to annual crops. Additionally, the forecasted temperature rise may accelerate plant

growth due to faster accumulation of growing degree days (GDD), shortening the growth cycle of annual crops like cereals, limiting their starch accumulation and grain-filling period, and thereby reducing their yields. In contrast, perennial crops like meadow hay are expected to benefit from the warmer climate, enabling greater biomass accumulation.

Figure 4. gross saleable product (€ ha⁻¹) for the nine crop rotation systems. Each system is characterized by farm type (crop production 'C', livestock production 'L'), management practices (conventional 'C' or organic 'O'), and residue management (removed '-R' or incorporated '+R'). Different bar colors indicate different crops. Shaded stacked bars indicate future climatic scenarios, with light and strong shades representing the periods 2040-2069 and 2070-2100, respectively.

Figure 5 presents the annual nitrogen (NO₃) leaching (kg ha⁻¹) for nine different rotation systems under both current and future conditions (2040 - 2069 in black dots, 2070 - 2100 in white dots). The baseline data reveals clear distinctions in NO₃ leaching between these systems. Crop production systems exhibit the highest NO₃ leaching, with values exceeding 10 kg ha⁻¹ in CO2+R, followed closely by CC+R and CC-R. The peak observed in CO2+R may be attributed to the high level of commercial organic fertilizers applied to oilseed rape, rye, and cereal-leguminous mixes. The incorporation of crop residues (+R) in conventional crop production systems slightly

increased NO_3 leaching, likely due to the elevated N inputs combined with mineral fertilizers, which can result in excess N leaching. Conversely, in CC2+R, where slurry was integrated with mineral fertilizer, and in CO+R, which had a restricted use of Ecolan, NO_3 leaching was substantially reduced ($< 8 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) compared to similar rotations without these specific practices. Livestock production systems (LC-R, LC+R, LO-R, LO+R) consistently display the lowest NO_3 leaching values ($< 5 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$). This result might be attributed to the presence of perennial crops like meadow hay, efficiently retaining N and contrasting leaching. Additionally, these systems had fewer than 50 days of bare soil, compared to over 100 days in crop production systems, further preserving the N pool. Residue incorporation (+R) had minimal effect, likely because the stability provided by perennial crops was already sufficient to maintain a balanced N cycle.

In future climate scenarios, NO_3 leaching showed an increasing trend across all systems, likely due to the more intense and altered precipitation patterns and accelerated N mineralization. The most significant increases were observed in crop production rotations, where NO_3 leaching may exceed 30 kg ha^{-1} by the 2070 - 2100 period, especially in CO2+R, where commercial organic fertilizers are consistently applied.

Livestock systems are expected to continue exhibiting lower NO_3 leaching under future conditions, remaining below 10 kg ha^{-1} by 2070 - 2100. Minimal differences between residue removal and incorporation are expected, as perennial crops like meadow may continue to mitigate NO_3 losses by improving N uptake and stabilizing soil N dynamics.

Figure 5. annual soil nitrate leaching (NO_3^- , kg ha^{-1}) for the nine crop rotation systems. Each system is characterized by farm type (C production 'C', livestock production 'L'), management practices (conventional 'C' or organic 'O'), and residue management (removed '-R' or incorporated '+R'). Dots indicate future climatic scenarios, with black and white representing the periods 2040-2069 and 2070-2100, respectively. The numbers within the bars indicate the number of annual bare soil days for each rotation.

Figure 6 shows the annual nitrous oxide (N_2O) emissions (kg ha^{-1}) for the nine rotation systems under both current and future conditions (2040 - 2069 in black dots, 2070 - 2100 in white dots). Under present condition (1999 - 2022), the highest emissions occur in crop production systems with values exceeding 1.0 kg ha^{-1} for CO_2+R , $\text{CC}+\text{R}$, and $\text{CC}-\text{R}$. $\text{CC}-\text{R}$. Notably, $\text{CC}-\text{R}$ exhibited higher emissions than $\text{CC}+\text{R}$, indicating a modest mitigation effect from residue incorporation. Emission in CO_2+R ($\sim 1.2 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$) were higher than in $\text{CO}+\text{R}$ ($\sim 0.75 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$), likely due to the broader application of commercial organic fertilizers, which, in the case of CO_2+R , were used not only on oilseed rape but also on rye and cereal-leguminous crops, potentially enhancing N_2O

release. Among the crop production systems, CC2+R, which integrated slurry with mineral fertilizer, recorded the lowest emissions ($\sim 0.55 \text{ kg ha}^{-1}$).

Livestock production systems (LC-R, LC+R, LO-R, LO+R) exhibited lower N_2O emissions on average compared to crop production systems, with values consistently below 0.75 kg ha^{-1} . This result could be likely attributed to the N-retentive properties of perennial crops like meadow, which may contribute to more stable N cycling. Additionally, these rotations had fewer than 50 days of bare soil, in contrast to crop production systems, which experienced over 100 days of bare soil. This prolonged soil cover may have further contributed to preserving the nitrogen pool by reducing nitrogen losses. Residue incorporation in these systems had minimal impact, probably because N dynamics were already stabilized by the long-term presence of hay grass.

In future climate scenarios, N_2O emissions rise across most systems, especially in crop production systems, with trends similar to that observed for NO_3 leaching. Emissions in CO2+R, CC-R, and CC+R surpassed 1.5 kg ha^{-1} by 2070–2100, likely due to enhanced N mineralization and microbial activity. The use of slurry in CC2+R intensified the rise in emissions compared to the respective rotation without organic fertilizer, although final values remained below 1.25 kg ha^{-1} . Livestock systems also showed slight increases in emissions, but these are projected to remain under 1 kg ha^{-1} even by 2070–2100.

Figure 6. annual soil nitrous oxide emission (N₂O, kg ha⁻¹) for the nine crop rotation systems. Each system is characterized by farm type (C production 'C', livestock production 'L'), management practices (conventional 'C' or organic 'O'), and residue management (removed '-R' or incorporated '+R'). Dots indicate future climatic scenarios, with black and white representing the periods 2040-2069 and 2070-2100, respectively. The numbers within the bars indicate the number of annual bare soil days for each rotation.

Figure 7 presents the annual change in soil carbon (ΔC , kg ha⁻¹) across nine rotation systems under both current (1999–2022) and future conditions (2040–2069 in black dots, 2070–2100 in white dots).

Under current conditions (1999–2022), all systems exhibit negative soil C balances, with the most pronounced losses observed in CC-R (exceeding -300 kg C ha⁻¹), likely due to the absence of crop residue retention and exclusive reliance on mineral fertilization, which limits organic matter inputs and accelerates soil organic carbon (SOC) depletion. LC-R follows closely, with losses over -250 kg C ha⁻¹. While residue incorporation in CC+R and LC+R marginally mitigates C loss in both crop and livestock production systems, it does not fully offset the decline in SOC. Among crop

production systems, CO2+R shows relatively lower C losses (between -150 and -200 kg C ha⁻¹), likely due to the synergistic effect of organic fertilizer application and residue management, which contribute to maintaining a higher input of organic matter. In livestock production systems, C losses are generally lower, with most systems showing losses below -200 kg C ha⁻¹, except for LC-R. The lower C depletion in these systems is likely attributed to the extended ground cover provided by perennial crops, which contribute continuous inputs of biomass, both above and below ground, enhancing SOC stability. The smallest C losses are observed in LO+R (between -100 and -150 kg C ha⁻¹), similar to the trend seen in organic crop production systems where residue retention is practiced.

Under future climate conditions, C losses intensified across most systems, with crop production systems experiencing more pronounced SOC depletion compared to livestock systems. CC-R showed the most severe losses, exceeding -400 kg C ha⁻¹, with residue incorporation (CC+R, CC2+R) providing only partial mitigation, insufficient to prevent substantial SOC depletion. Organic crop production systems also experienced accelerated C depletion, though losses remain below -400 kg C ha⁻¹, reflecting some resilience due to organic management practices. In contrast, livestock systems exhibit smaller increases in SOC losses, never exceeding -350 kg C ha⁻¹, indicating higher resilience in maintaining soil C stocks under future climate conditions. This resilience may be due to the longer growing periods and root biomass contribution of perennial species like meadow, which enhance C inputs and improve soil structure, thereby reducing the vulnerability of these systems to climate-induced SOC losses.

Figure 7. annual soil carbon stock changes (C, kg ha⁻¹) for the nine crop rotation systems. Each system is characterized by farm type (C production 'C', livestock production 'L'), management practices (conventional 'C' or organic 'O'), and residue management (removed '-R' or incorporated '+R'). Dots indicate future climatic scenarios, with black and white representing the periods 2040-2069 and 2070-2100, respectively. The numbers within the bars indicate the number of annual bare soil days for each rotation.

2.2. Trade-off analysis through the Σ ommit index application

Figure 8 presents the evaluation of nine rotation systems using the Σ ommit Index, a fuzzy-logic-based composite index that integrates four trade-off components - soil C stock, N₂O emissions, NO₃⁻ leaching, and crop yield - into a single sustainability metric, ranging from 0 (poor) to 1 (optimal). The red diamonds represent the Σ ommit Index values under the balanced scenario, where equal weight (25%) is assigned to each of the four components. The three facets - Young farmers, Agrochem corporation, and CAP paying agency - depict different stakeholder narratives. For each of these narratives, the weights assigned to the trade-off components were redistributed according to expert judgment, reflecting the specific sustainability goals and

perspectives of these stakeholder groups. The box plots within each facet illustrate how the distribution of Σ ommit Index values shifts in these alternative scenarios compared to the balanced scenario (red diamonds).

Under the balanced scenario, the highest Σ ommit Index values (>0.75) were observed in the organically managed rotations LO+R, LO-R, and CO+R, likely due to the integration of perennial crops in livestock production systems and the incorporation of crop residues where applied. These systems demonstrate high sustainability by maintaining both high crop yields and low environmental impacts (N_2O emissions, NO_3 leaching, and C losses). In contrast, the CC-R system showed the lowest Σ ommit Index value (~ 0.5), due to elevated N_2O emissions, NO_3 leaching, and substantial C losses, which negatively affected its sustainability.

In the Young farmers narrative, all rotation systems displayed lower Σ ommit Index values compared to the balanced scenario, with the most pronounced decreases observed in CC-R (-62%) and CC+R (-44%). In this narrative, experts placed the highest weight on crop yield, followed by soil C stock, while N_2O emissions and NO_3 leaching were considered less important. The significant Σ ommit Index drop in CC-R and CC+R could be attributed to the low gross sealable product generated by these rotations (below 4000 € ha^{-1}), coupled with higher NO_3 leaching and, particularly for CC-R, the highest N_2O emissions and C losses.

The Agrochem corporation and CAP paying agency narratives exhibited similar trends, with the Σ ommit Index distributions displaying wider ranges and more overlap with the balanced scenario. In particular, rotations such as LC-R, LC+R, and CC2+R showed parts of their box plots exceeding the red diamonds, indicating that these systems occasionally received higher evaluations under these narratives compared to the balanced scenario. In these narratives, the focus shifted: while crop yield was prioritized in the Young farmers narrative, the Agrochem corporation assigned greater importance to N losses, and the CAP paying agency emphasized soil C stock. Therefore, in these two narratives - especially in the CAP paying agency - the environmental impact of the systems was weighed more heavily than their productivity. As a result, systems like LC-R, LC+R, and CC2+R, which had lower yields but reduced N and C losses, were less penalized and received higher index values, with distributions that sometimes exceeded those of the balanced scenario.

Overall, organically managed rotations generally received the highest Σ ommit Index values, with narrow distributions close to the diamonds across all three narratives, except for CO2+R. Despite achieving the highest yields and limited C losses, CO2+R recorded the highest levels of N losses through emissions and leaching, leading to lower Σ ommit Index values across all the narratives.

Figure 8. Σ ommit Index distribution for the nine rotation systems across three stakeholder narratives: Young farmers, Agrochemical corporation, and CAP paying agency. Box plots represent the distribution of Σ ommit Index values for each rotation under each of the three narratives. Red diamonds indicate the Σ ommit Index values based on a balanced weighting scheme, where each trade-off component is equally weighted.

Figure 9 illustrates the Σ ommit Index values for nine rotation systems under three climate scenarios: 1999 - 2022 (red squares), 2040 - 2069 (green diamonds), and 2070 - 2100 (purple circles).

In future climate scenarios, most systems exhibited a marked decline in the Σ ommit Index, with the most significant decreases observed in CO2+R, CC-R, and CC+R (-68%, -64% and -64% respectively, in 2070-2100 scenario). The decline in sustainability in these systems could be likely

due to the reduced productive performance of annual crop rotations and the exacerbated N emissions and leaching, and C loss. Organic management practices and crop residues incorporations appeared insufficient to offset these negative impacts on climatic change in these rotations.

In contrast, rotations such as LO+R, LO-R, LC+R, and LC-R showed relatively minor declines in the Σ ommit Index, indicating. Notably, the LC-R system even exhibited a slight increase (+2 %) in the Σ ommit Index in the 2070 - 2100 scenario, likely due to increased gross saleable yield, particularly from meadow hay, which compensated for the reduced yields of cereals.

These results suggested that including perennial crops in rotations, which provide extended soil cover, a longer productive period, and contribute to soil organic matter inputs, could enhance the farming system capacity to maintain productivity and reduce environmental impacts in response to climate change.

Figure 9. Σ ommit Index values for the nine rotation systems under current climatic conditions (red squares), 2040–2069 (purple circles), and 2070–2100 (green diamonds).

2.3. Soil microbiome response to extreme events

This task was set up on the assumption that soil fungi and bacteria are responsible for 80-90% of soil metabolic activity and therefore are excellent indicators of soil functioning (Fierer, 2017). Furthermore, the possibility of directly measuring the quantity of fungi and bacteria into the soil by molecular means allows quantitative changes in populations to be measured much more accurately than the common biochemical approaches such chloroform fumigation-extraction (CFE) and substrate-induced respiration (SIR) (Semenov et al., 2018).

Soil microbial biomass (sum of total fungi e bacteria copy number) resulted significantly higher after warm spring thus suggesting that a cereal sown in middle March, after two months (on middle-late May) can be supported by a better soil functioning as compared the here simulated cold spring (Table 5).

As far as water availability is concerned, the lower water content, corresponding to a water content of 20% Field Capacity, in order to maintain a continuous plant water stress, caused a decrease in microbial biomass, thus leading to the hypothesis of a decrease in soil function (Table 5).

Table 5. Means of the sum of fungi and bacteria in term of number of copies per μ of soil DNA subjected to two-way ANOVA.

	Count	Mean n. copies μ l ⁻¹ soil DNA	P-Value
Temp			0.000
Cold	9	260681	b¹
Warm	9	453474	a
Water content			0.0250
Field Capacity 20%	6	293589	b
Field Capacity 80%	6	373293	a
Field Capacity 110%	6	404350	a
Temp by Water			ns
Cold; FC20	3	224352	
Cold; FC80	3	251873	
Cold; FC110	3	305819	
Warm; FC20	3	362827	
Warm; FC80	3	494714	
Warm; FC110	3	502881	

An additional interesting finding can be deduced from the significant difference according to Bonferroni pairwise comparison of Fungi-to-Bacteria ratio (Table 6) in response to cold and warm springs. The balance between fungi and bacteria, which differs according to temperature (Table 6), increases under cold spring, and decrease under the warmer spring regime as shown in Figure 10. These changes in the balance between the two main microbial taxa of soil microbiome may indicate qualitative variations in soil functions, which can be linked to the quantitative changes observed in the total microbial biomass. Specifically, cold temperature induces a significant decrease in microbial biomass associated with a shift toward fungi of the fungial to bacterial ratio (Table 5, Figure 10); whereas warm spring increases microbial biomass by inducing a reduction of that ratio (Table 6, Figure 10).

Table 6. Non parametric analysis of the difference of the Fungal-to-Bacterial ratio difference under cold and warm spring.

	Count	Mean
Temperature regimes		Mean F/B
Cold spring	9	0.0423536
Warm spring	9	0.0188598

Kruskal-Wallis Test and Bonferroni Pairwise comparison P-Value ≤ 0.055

Figure 10. Box-and-Whisker Plot of the Fungi-to-Bacteria ratio after a cold and warm spring regimes

The whole dataset of fungal and bacterial response has been made available for developing a model of soil functionality variation in opposite potential climatic variations due to climatic change.

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3. Conclusions

Loss of soil organic matter is a critical issue in northern countries. This paper presents an a priori method for assessing the effects of different cropping systems on productivity, soil carbon, and nitrogen dynamics using a process-based simulation model. Although the model was calibrated with regional statistical data, it effectively simulates the behaviour of both conventional and organic systems under current and future climate conditions. The results show that maintaining or increasing soil organic matter is particularly challenging in the studied environment, and this issue is projected to worsen under future climate scenarios.

Under current conditions, organic rotations that incorporate perennial crops, crop residue, green manure, and stable carbon fertilizers demonstrated the highest sustainability, as indicated by the Σ ommit Index. These systems outperformed conventional ones in terms of both productivity and reduced environmental impacts. Conventional systems, particularly those without crop residue incorporation, exhibited the lowest sustainability.

Future climate scenarios predict a substantial decline in the sustainability of most systems, particularly those dominated by annual crops. This decline is driven by reduced yields, increased nitrogen losses, and accelerated soil carbon depletion, suggesting that current organic practices may be insufficient to meet the challenges posed by climate change. Exploring new organic and conservation cropping systems will be essential to address these challenges effectively.

Regarding the simulation of the microbial biomass response to temperature and soil water content, the results confirm that, referring to the climatic conditions of the eastern Po Valley in northern Italy, the microbial biomass almost doubles in warm springs compared to those where the temperature trend is lower than the seasonal average. Furthermore, soil microbial biomass is much more sensitive to prolonged dry periods than to prolonged wet periods.

The significant variation of the fungal/bacterial ratio in response to temperature suggests that changes in spring temperature may induce changes in soil functionality, however those changes should be considered as a microbiome variation trend in the long period. Indeed, as shown in this study, the fungal-to-bacterial ratio can vary significantly in the short term (60 days in this case), suggesting that the balance between soil fungi and bacteria varies continuously over the seasons.

Considering that soil microbiome can vary according to soil type, climate and land use and that microorganisms have a variety of evolutionary adaptations and physiological acclimation mechanisms, it is very difficult to generalize the impact of climate change. Therefore, when modelling the microbial response to climatic changes, the main responses here obtained of the microbial biomass to changes in temperature and water content in spring soils must be considered.

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